

Towards verifying unsafe Rust programs against Rust's pointer-aliasing restrictions: Technical Report

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Abstract. This TR defines a program logic for a toy language that captures the following features of Rust's pointer aliasing rules: mutable references (including two-phase borrows), shared references, protection of function arguments, boxes, and UnsafeCell.

Keywords: Rust · Formal verification · Pointer-aliasing

1 The mini-language λ_{PA}

Provenance	pr	\in	$OwningProv \cup MutRefProv \cup SharedRefProv$	
Pointer	p	$::=$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} prov : Provenance \\ address : \mathbb{N} \end{array} \right\}$	
OwningPointer	p_{own}	\in	$\{p \mid p.prov \in OwningProv\}$	
MutRef	$p_{\&mut}$	\in	$\{p \mid p.prov \in MutRefProv\}$	
SharedRef	$p_{\&}$	\in	$\{p \mid p.prov \in SharedRefProv\}$	
Type	τ	$::=$	$int \mid \&\tau \mid \&mut \tau \mid *\tau$ $\mid UnsafeCell<\tau> \mid Box<\tau>$	
Scalar	σ	$::=$	$p \mid z$	$z \in \mathbb{Z}$
Value	v	$::=$	$\sigma \mid \text{rec } f(x_1: \tau_1, \dots, x_n: \tau_n): \tau_f = e$	
Variable	x			
PureExpr	ε	$::=$	$v \mid x$	
Expr	e	$::=$	v $\mid \text{new}(\varepsilon) \mid \text{free}(\varepsilon)$ $\mid \&_*\varepsilon \mid \&mut \ * \varepsilon$ $\mid *\varepsilon \mid *\varepsilon := \varepsilon$ $\mid \text{protect}_\tau(\varepsilon) \mid \text{unprotect}_\tau(\varepsilon)$ $\mid \text{let } x := e_1 \text{ in } e_2$ $\mid \varepsilon(\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n)$ $\mid e_1; e_2$	

$e_1; e_2$ is syntactic sugar for $\text{let } _ = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$

Note that the type parameter in $\text{protect}_\tau(\varepsilon)$ is the expected type of ε , while the type parameter in $\&_*p$ describes the static type of the value pointed to by p .

<pre> 1 fn write(mut x: Box<i32>, y: & mut i32) -> Box<i32> { 2 let z = y as *mut i32; 3 *x = 5; 4 *y = 10; 5 unsafe { *z = 15 }; 6 x 7 } 8 9 let b = Box::new(23); 10 let mut root = 0; 11 let tmp = &mut root; 12 13 write(b, tmp); </pre>	<pre> 1 let write := rec f(x: Box<int>, y: &mut int) : Box<int> := (2 let z := y in 3 *x := 5; 4 *y := 10; 5 *z := 15; 6 x 7) in 8 9 let b := new(32) in 10 11 let tmp := new(0) in 12 13 write(b, tmp) </pre>
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Table 1. An example of a Rust program (L), and its translation to λ_{PA} (R).

2 The separation logic

Resources	r	$::=$	$p \mapsto \sigma \mid p_1 \Downarrow p_2 \mid p_1 \Uparrow p_2 \mid p_1 \blacklozenge p_2$	
Heaps	h	\in	$Resources \rightarrow [0, 1]$	
Assertions	a	\in	$\mathcal{P}(Heaps)$	
	$a_1 * a_2$	\triangleq	$\{h \mid \exists h_1 \in a_1, h_2 \in a_2. h_1 + h_2 = h\}$	
	emp	\triangleq	$\{\lambda r. 0\}$	
	$\text{own}_q r$	\triangleq	$\{(\lambda r'. 0)[r := q]\}$	$q \in (0, 1]$
	$p \xrightarrow{q} \sigma$	\triangleq	$\text{own}_q p \mapsto \sigma$	
	$p \Downarrow p'$	\triangleq	$\text{own}_q p \Downarrow p'$	
	$p' \Uparrow p$	\triangleq	$\text{own}_q p' \Uparrow p$	
	$p' \blacklozenge p$	\triangleq	$\text{own}_q p' \blacklozenge p$	

$p \mapsto \sigma$ is syntactic sugar for $p \xrightarrow{1} \sigma$ when it is clear from the context whether the assertion or the resource is meant, likewise with $p' \Uparrow p$ and $p \Downarrow p'$

View Shift

$$P \Rightarrow Q$$

$$\frac{\text{VS-TRANSITIVE} \quad P \Rightarrow R \quad R \Rightarrow Q}{P \Rightarrow Q}$$

$$\frac{\text{VS-FRAME} \quad P \Rightarrow Q}{R * P \Rightarrow Q * R}$$

$$\frac{\text{VS-SUBSET} \quad P \subseteq Q}{P \Rightarrow Q}$$

Phase Transitions

$$P \Rightarrow Q$$

$$\frac{\text{RESERVATION-END}}{p \xrightarrow{\frac{1}{2}} \sigma * p \Downarrow p' \Rightarrow p' \xrightarrow{\frac{1}{2}} \sigma * p' \Uparrow p}$$

$$\frac{\text{REFERENCE-END}}{p' \xrightarrow{q} \sigma * p' \Uparrow p \Rightarrow p \xrightarrow{q} \sigma}$$

Hoare Triples $\boxed{\{P\} e \{Q\}}$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{H-VIEW-SHIFT-CONSEQUENCE} \\ \frac{P \Rightarrow P' \quad \{P'\} e \{Q\} \quad Q \Rightarrow Q'}{\{P\} e \{Q'\}} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{H-FRAME} \\ \frac{\{P\} e \{Q\}}{\{R * P\} e \{Q * R\}} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{H-EXISTS} \\ \frac{\forall x. \{P(x)\} e \{Q\}}{\{\exists x. P(x)\} e \{Q\}} \end{array}$$

Expressions $\boxed{\{P\} e \{Q\}}$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{NEW} \\ \{\mathbf{emp}\} \text{new}(\sigma) \{r. r \mapsto \sigma * r \in \text{OwningPointer}\} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{FREE} \\ \{p_{\text{own}} \mapsto \sigma\} \text{free}(p_{\text{own}}) \{\mathbf{emp}\} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{WRITE} \\ \{p \mapsto \sigma_{\text{old}}\} *p := \sigma \{p \mapsto \sigma\} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{READ} \\ \{p \overset{q}{\mapsto} \sigma\} *p \{r. p \overset{q}{\mapsto} \sigma * r = \sigma\} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LET} \\ \frac{\{P\} e_1 \{r. R(r)\} \quad \forall v. \{R(v)\} e_2[v/x] \{Q\}}{\{P\} \text{let } x := e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \{Q\}} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{RESERVE-MUTABLE-BORROW} \\ \{p \mapsto \sigma\} \&\text{mut } *p \{r. p \overset{\frac{1}{2}}{\mapsto} \sigma * p \overset{\frac{1}{2}}{\Downarrow} r * r \overset{\frac{1}{2}}{\mapsto} \sigma\} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{SHARED-BORROW-UNSAFECELL} \\ \{\mathbf{emp}\} \&\text{UnsafeCell}_{\langle \tau \rangle} *p \{r. r = p\} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{SHARED-BORROW-NO-UNSAFECELL} \\ \frac{\nexists \tau'. \tau = \text{UnsafeCell}_{\langle \tau' \rangle}}{\{p \overset{q}{\mapsto} \sigma\} \&\tau *p \{r. p \overset{\frac{q}{2}}{\mapsto} \sigma * r \overset{\frac{q}{2}}{\mapsto} \sigma * r \overset{\frac{q}{2}}{\Uparrow} p\}} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{CALL} \\ \frac{\{P\} \text{let } x := \text{protect}_{\tau}(v) \text{ in let } \text{res} = e \text{ in } \overline{\text{unprotect}_{\tau}(x); \text{unprotect}_{\tau_f}(\text{protect}_{\tau_f}(\text{res}))} \{r. Q(r)\}}{\{P\} (\text{rec } f(\bar{x} : \bar{\tau}) : \tau_f = e)(\bar{v}) \{r. Q(r)\}} \end{array}$$

Protection $\boxed{\{P\} \text{protect}_{\tau}(\varepsilon) \{Q\}}$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{PROTECT-NO-OP} \\ \frac{\exists \tau'. \tau \in \{\text{int}, * \tau'\}}{\{\mathbf{emp}\} \text{protect}_{\tau}(\sigma) \{r. r = \sigma\}} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PROTECT-UNSAFECELL} \\ \frac{\{P\} \text{protect}_{\tau}(\sigma) \{Q\}}{\{P\} \text{protect}_{\text{UnsafeCell}_{\langle \tau \rangle}}(\sigma) \{Q\}} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{PROTECT-SHAREDREF} \\ \frac{\{P\} \&\tau *p \{r. \exists q. Q(r, q) * r \overset{q}{\Uparrow} p\}}{\{P\} \text{protect}_{\&\tau}(p) \{r. \exists q. Q(r, q) * r \overset{q}{\Downarrow} p\}} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PROTECT-MUTREF} \\ \frac{\{P\} \&\text{mut } *p \{r. Q(r) * r \overset{q}{\Uparrow} p\}}{\{P\} \text{protect}_{\&\text{mut } \tau}(p) \{r. Q(r) * r \overset{q}{\Downarrow} p\}} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{PROTECT-BOX} \\ \frac{\{P\} \&\text{mut } *p \{r. Q(r) * r \overset{q}{\Uparrow} p\}}{\{P\} \text{protect}_{\text{Box}_{\langle \tau \rangle}}(p) \{r. Q(r) * r \in \text{OwningPointer}\}} \end{array}$$

Unprotection $\{ P \} \text{unprotect}(\varepsilon) \{ Q \}$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{UNPROTECT-NO-OP} \\
\frac{\exists \tau'. \tau \in \{ * \tau', \text{Box} \langle \tau' \rangle, \text{int} \}}{\{ \mathbf{emp} \} \text{unprotect}_\tau(\sigma) \{ r. r = \sigma \}} \\
\\
\text{UNPROTECT-UNSAFECELL} \\
\frac{\{ P \} \text{unprotect}_\tau(\sigma) \{ Q \}}{\{ P \} \text{unprotect}_{\text{UnsafeCell} \langle \tau \rangle}(\sigma) \{ Q \}} \\
\\
\text{UNPROTECT-REFERENCE} \\
\frac{\exists \tau'. \tau \in \{ \& \tau', \&\text{mut } \tau' \}}{\{ p' \overset{q}{\bullet} p \} \text{unprotect}_\tau(p') \{ r. p' \overset{q}{\uparrow} p * r = p' \}}
\end{array}$$

Above logic extends the one from our paper with the following features:

Functions **CALL** ensures that references passed as function arguments for parameters of reference type stay alive for the duration of the call through the protection mechanism. Also, mutable references and boxes are reborrowed, to satisfy the rule that the memory they point to must only be accessed through the argument or a pointer derived from the argument.

Boxes Boxes are largely treated like `&mut`, in accordance with the Rust Reference, except for the fact that, when protected a new pointer with different provenance is created to replace the old one, like a reborrow without a reference-end resource.

UnsafeCell A value of type `UnsafeCell< τ >` is generally handled the same way as a value of type τ , only reborrowing a pointer to an `UnsafeCell< τ >` is treated as the identity function, as the reborrow should not change the mutability of the pointer.

Two-Phase Borrows Two-Phase Borrowing¹ [1] is a relaxation of the classical aliasing rules for mutable references, where a mutably borrowed reference need not be exclusive for its entire lifetime, but rather only for a contiguous part of its lifetime. The mutable reference is now *reserved* rather than borrowed immediately. At the reservation point, no conflicting live mutable borrows may exist, and the Rust Reference also encourages making it so there are no conflicting live *shared* borrows either. Once reserved, the reference is treated similarly to a shared reference right up until the reservation is ended using **RESERVATION-END**, at which point it must satisfy the classical aliasing restrictions for mutable references. Note that combining **RESERVE-MUTABLE-BORROW** and **RESERVATION-END** results in the mutable borrow rule from our paper.

References

1. Villani, N., Hostert, J., Dreyer, D., Jung, R.: Tree borrows **9**, 188:1019–188:1042. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3735592>, <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3735592>

¹ https://rustc-dev-guide.rust-lang.org/borrow_check/two_phase_borrows.html